

H2020-FNR-2020-2 Project no. 101000560

Rapid discovery and development of enzymes for novel and greener consumer products

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

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Duration: 4 years

D5.3 – Second set of LCA reports

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Deliverable N°:	5.3
Lead Beneficiary:	SUSMOM
Other participants:	
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D5.3 (M36) focuses on the cradle-to-gate life-cycle-assessment (LCA) of a RADICALZ process dealing with the production of 1 kilogram of a nutraceutical. The synthesis comprises several sub-units, and two potential synthetic routes (chemo-enzymatic, route A, or fully enzymatic, route B). As sub-units, biomass recollection, and pre-processing are excluded from the assessment, while transportation, biomass extraction, substrate enrichment, chemical hydrolysis (Route A), enzymatic oxidation (Route A), or enzymatic hydrolysis and oxidation (Route B) are assessed. As impact categories, Total Energy Consumption, Abiotic Depletion Potential, Water Depletion, and Global Warming Potential are considered. Others (Eutrophication, Acidification, and Human Toxicity) are briefly contextualized as well.

Overall, the production shows an environmental impact comparable to other biorefinery-like processes reported in the literature, with a Total Energy Demand in the range of $3500 \text{ MJ} \cdot \text{kg Product}^{-1}$ and a generation of $1250\text{--}1400 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{eq} \cdot \text{kg Product}^{-1}$. Importantly, 500 kg of pre-processed biomass are used, and the energy content of that residue – once substrate is extracted –, may cover a significant proportion of the energy demand of the process (through combustion). Likewise, ~60 % of the produced CO_2 is biogenic, and considered to be “neutral”. The rest of CO_2 comes from electricity, which can be reduced if renewable energy sources are included (e.g. hydropower). The current lab-scale process has still areas with significant environmental impact, and several mitigation actions can be put forth to diminish that impact considerably.

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